

EVOLUTION OF CRYSTALLINITY WITH MULTIPLE LAMINATION STEPS IN HIGH PERFORMANCE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY IN-SITU CONSOLIDATION PROCESS

I. Esguerra-Arce ^{*1,2}, M.I. Martín^{1,3}, A. Pérez-Pastor¹ and V. García-Martínez¹

¹FIDAMC, Foundation for the Research, Development and Application of Composite Materials,
Avda. Rita Levi Montalcini 29, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain

Ingrid.Esguerra.External@fidamc.es

²Universidad Carlos III de Madrid

Avda. de la Universidad 30, 28911, Leganés, Spain

³Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Pza. del Cardenal Cisneros, 3, 28040, Madrid, Spain

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ABSTRACT

In this study the behavior of different thermoplastic composite materials with PEEK and PEKK matrixes in automatic lay-up and in-situ consolidation process was evaluated. Although multiple physical and chemical phenomena are interacting, this research contains several results on regarding to the degree of consolidation and also crystallinity of the samples. When non-self-heated tooling was employed, a marked phenomenon of cold crystallization was observed especially in the first layers. In contrast, the extent of crystallinity remained nearly constant when the automated lay-up was performed over a self-heated tooling. Moreover, it was possible to observe that increasing the number of layers contributed to reduce the internal porosity, so the degree of bonding increased with the number of consolidation steps.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of engineering thermoplastics such as polyetheretherketone (PEEK), polyetherketoneketone (PEKK) or polyaryletherketone (PAEK) in carbon fibre reinforced components has been growing continuously in aerospace applications. These thermoplastic composites are becoming the material of choice for replacing traditional metallic materials because higher strength to weight ratios, better chemical and impact resistance and design flexibility.

Besides thermoplastics have recognized aspects such as excellent Fire, Smoke, and Toxicity (FST) properties, higher mechanical properties and damage tolerance, chemical resistance, infinite shop life, weld ability of thermoplastic components, reuse of material and shorter manufacturing cycles compared to their competitor thermosets. Thermoplastic resins offer a high potential not only regarding material properties, but also in order to reduce processing, logistic, operation and life cycle costs.

In-situ consolidation is currently one of the most important processes considered with the goal of scaling-up thermoplastic composite materials to a verifiable industrial production. New trends based on manufacturing of wing skin covers and aircraft fuselage panels using this technology are showing the renewed interest of aerospace industry on it.

After being studied for many years, it is possible to find many information concerning lamination trials with CF/PEEK base composites. However, due to the new developments of material suppliers, different alternatives are focusing the interest of manufacturers.

This study tries to show the behaviour of different thermoplastic composite materials under the automatic lay-up and in-situ consolidation manufacturing technique. Although multiple physical and chemical phenomena are interacting, this research contains several results on regarding to the degree of consolidation and also crystallinity of the samples.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and manufacturing process

Different UD-thermoplastic composite materials (PAEK family) in ¼” width form have been laminated with a single-tow deposition machine using a laser scanning as heating source. The lamination strategy was conducted in a way that the laminate has the shape of a ladder. By proceeding this way it was possible to extract testing specimens composed by one layer, two layers, ..., n-1 layers and n layers (being ‘n’ the maximum number of layers in the laminate).

This strategy permits to observe that this manufacturing technique is dynamic and its results evolve with rising lamination steps. This effect has been pointed out by other authors as Khan et al. [1] simulating the increasing in the degree of intimate contact whilst lamination or Hoang [2] which determines the higher void content carried by the last layers of the laminate because the less number of re-processing steps.

Development of thermal residual stresses is one of the most important limitations of this technique [3], resulting in incorrect final dimensions of produced parts or shape distortions. The use of self-heated tooling is normally shown as the most profitable way to reduce its impact, this study is not devoted to analyze this issue but due to the importance of self-heated tooling in the evolution of crystallization, the same sample for each material has been produced by considering self and non-self-heated tooling.

2.2 Characterization

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) tests were performed in a TA Instruments Q2000 calorimeter with N₂ as purge gas. The samples were placed in aluminum pans and hermetically sealed. The dynamic tests on composite samples were carried out at the heating rates of 20 °C/min in a temperature range from room temperature to 390°C in order to evaluate the extent of crystallinity evolution in every lamination step when a self-heated and non-self-heated tooling was employed.

In addition, a complete study of void progression during the lamination of different plies as well as the degree of contact between each layer was also studied by means of optical microscopy. A Nikon Eclipse LV150 219 microscope equipped with a camera was employed for this analysis. Cross sections have been polished with an automatic polisher. For roughing, sandpapers were used from 100 to 1200 FEPA with water. For polishing, cloths and solutions with diamond particles from were employed.

3 RESULTS

Thermograms of different materials showed that when non-self-heated tooling was employed, a marked phenomenon of cold crystallization appears in the first layers. This exothermic peak completely disappeared from the seven ply for PEEK laminate (Fig.1) while in PEKK panel continued appearing in all layers although the cold crystallization enthalpy decreased when the number of layers increase (Fig.2). For PEEK laminate, the maximum extent of crystallinity was reached when layer nine is positioned and then this value remained nearly constant when the rest of layer are placed (Fig.3). For PEKK the higher value of crystallinity was achieved in layer eleven, probably due to the different crystallization kinetics associated to both materials.

Figure 1: DSC thermograms of specimens composed by different number of layers [(@20°C Tool) – APC2/AS4]

Figure 2: DSC thermograms of specimens composed by different number of layers [(@20°C Tool) – PEKK/THS45]

Figure 3: Evolution of crystallinity for every layer positioned [(@20°C Tool) – PEKK/THS45]

A probable explanation of this evidence is the huge difference in the cooling profiles when the layer is far from the tool as is described in Figure 4, where cooling profiles change into slower ones during lamination of the upper layers of the laminate.

Figure 4: Thermocouples measurements TC1 between layers 1&2 laying the 3th and TC2 between layers 22&23 laying the 24th

When a self-heated tooling was applied in the automated lamination and in-situ consolidation process the effect of cold crystallization disappeared for both materials as can be appreciated in Figure 5 for PEKK laminate. In this situation, the high crystallinity observed in the first layer was developed during the isothermal stabilization over the self-heated tooling. In the subsequent stages to positioned material, the substrate material was always in a crystallinity state due to the tool isothermal temperature.

Figure 5: DSC thermograms of specimens composed by different number of layers [(@200°C Tool) – PEKK/THS45]

These results showed that there are differences in the crystallization kinetics for all thermoplastic materials and so the results of the process will be to some extent affected by the selected material and the tool temperature set. The technique should be established on regarding to the particular material used.

On the other hand, the degree of bonding was evaluated by taking into account only the inter-laminar void presence. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the evolution of porosity during the lay-up of different plies in ISC process (from the 4th to the 8th layer) with a 20 °C and 200° C tool. It is possible to see that increasing the number of layers contribute to reduce the internal porosity both for self-heated and non- self-heated tool. This valuable information is a key aspect for determining the number of re-consolidation steps required to obtain the whole consolidation of the laminates.

Fig. 3: Evolution of void content with the increasing number of layers [(@20°C Tool) – APC2/AS4]

Fig. 4: Evolution of void content with the increasing number of layers [(@200°C Tool) – APC2/AS4]

9 CONCLUSIONS

The analysis carried out in this document has permitted to obtain information about the tendencies in crystallization whilst automatic lamination and in-situ consolidation is applied by using different thermoplastic composite materials. The crystallization kinetics of the different matrices rules the evolution of the results.

The observed differences between both kinds of tools are a clear representation of the high impact of the temperature and cooling profiles in these materials. The results have permitted to understand in a better way the thermal distributions in the laminates, where probably the layers closer to the tooling experience abrupt cooling profiles.

Microscopic evaluation showed that when the number of layers increased during the automated lay-up and in-situ consolidation process, a marked decreasing in the internal porosity was appreciated both for self-heated and non- self-heating tool.

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